

HISTORICAL PERIODS OF THE FORMATION OF ECOTOURISM IN THE WORLD.

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The modern world strives for a more responsible and sustainable use of natural resources, and in this regard, the field of ecotourism is becoming more and more relevant. Ecotourism is one of the fastest growing areas of the travel industry, combining the interest in natural beauty and ecosystems with the principles of nature conservation and sustainable development.

Humanity is moving to cities. Huge agglomerations swallow more and more people and fill their lives with noise. Stress is a constant companion of the urban lifestyle, the conditions of which do not correspond to the psychological or physiological needs of a person. One of the human-biological species, individual earthlings cannot completely "get out" of nature, no matter how much they want to. City dwellers are drawn to nature to be alone with it, to get fresh air. This kind of activity is called tourism all over the world.

Analyzing the concept of ecotourism using the main categories "Ecology" and "tourism" allows us to more fully reveal its essence and content. Ecotourism is a holistic concept that combines two important areas of activity - environmental protection and tourism. To fully understand ecotourism, it is necessary to study the meaning and history of the terms "ecology" and "tourism" in depth.

It is known that the term ecology (from the Greek oikos - home, dwelling and logos - teaching) was first used by the German scientist E. Haeckel in his book "General Morphology of Organisms" in 1866, he defined this concept as the environment of organisms. offers to determine the relationship with the environment.

The word tourism is derived from the French word "tour" and means a walk and a trip. It is used in the sense of "tourism" in a narrow sense - travel, recreation, and people's trips to tourist attractions¹. Agreeing with the above, these travelers aren't looking for luxury hotels and fine dining, they're looking for an authentic and immersive experience. For them, travel is not only a physical activity, but also a spiritual journey that changes their outlook on life

¹ Краткий словарь иностранных слов.- М.: «Изд.иностр.и нац. слов», 1958.- 404с.

and the world around them. "Tourism" in a narrow sense is not limited only to travel - it is a way of life, a philosophy, a way of seeing the world with open eyes and heart. These travelers don't just walk the path, they create their own paths filled with adventure, enrichment and inspiration".

The health aspect of tourism cannot be ignored. Many people are looking for opportunities to get back to nature, get fresh air, and improve their physical and mental health. Hiking, health spas, eco-tours help to increase health and vital energy.

Thus, tourism means not only an opportunity to change the scenery, but also a multifaceted adventure that promotes recreation, knowledge, health and spiritual enrichment. After all, "Ecology is a social condition that connects man with nature"².

Today, many scientists interpret the scientific views on the concept of ecotourism with their own views. In particular, in the opinion of research scientist Kh. Djurakulov, "In other words, determining the essence and functional significance of any concept depends first of all on their scientific and theoretical foundations. Including, the history of the formation and development of the concept of ecotourism, the philosophical justification of its types and classification, at the same time, it is distinguished by the fact that it is aimed at increasing the role of human development in ensuring the ecological stability of today³.

In the 18th and 19th centuries, with the emergence of scientific research and interest in nature, expeditions and trips for scientific purposes began to develop. After this period, the first steps in the formation of ecological consciousness can be observed.

The term "Ecotourism" itself began to be actively used in the 20th century. After the Second World War, the era of mass tourism began, but at the same time, awareness of its negative impact on nature began. In response, there was a need to develop sustainable forms of tourism that take into account respect for nature and cultural heritage.

In fact, although this field was developed as an independent direction of tourism in the 70s of the 20th century, the term "ecotourism" was officially used for the first time in 1983 by the Mexican ecologist-economist Hector Ceballos-

² Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси. 10-жилд. –Т.: «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси» Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2005. –Б. 164

³ Джуракулов Х.А. Ўзбекистонда замонавий экотуризмни ривожлантиришда шахс экологик ҳукукий онгини юксалтириш зарурати / Х.Джуракулов. –Самарқанд: “Самарқанд давлат чет тиллар институти” нашриёти, 2022. – 8 б.

Lascurein. He uses this concept "in the sense of traveling to the cultural attractions located in these areas, as well as specimens of wild flora and fauna to get to know and study the places of nature relatively untouched by man"⁴. After that, several definitions of ecological tourism appeared. In particular, according to the definition of the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO): "Ecotourism includes all forms of nature tourism, in which the main desire of tourists is to observe and communicate with nature"⁵.

In conclusion, it can be noted that ecotourism is not only a form of recreation, but also a way to help save the planet for future generations. By following the principles of ecotourism, we can enjoy the beauty of nature, respect cultural heritage and promote the balance between man and nature. The correct implementation and development of ecotourism requires a deep understanding of its theoretical and methodological foundations, as well as a constant effort to protect nature and a harmonious relationship with the environment.

References:

1. Краткий словарь иностранных слов.- М.: «Изд.инostr.и нац. слов», 1958.- 404с.
2. Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси. 10-жилд. -Т.: «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси» Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2005. –Б. 164
3. Ceballos Lascurain H. The Future of Ecotourism // Mexico journal.1984. – P. 13-14.

⁴ Ceballos Lascurain H. The Future of Ecotourism // Mexico journal.1984. –P. 13-14.

⁵ Мозговая О.С. Инструменты управления развитием экологического туризма в регионах мира // Белорусский журнал международного права и международных отношений. –Белорусь, 2004. — № 2. –Ст. 90.